

Ultra-Low-Latency Wireless Audio Headphones for Metal Detectors

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*Internal integration of the electronic module on an acoustic plate
without external housing or functional modification of the shell*

Figure 1: Prototype of ultra-low-latency wireless audio headphones with internal integration of the electronic module inside the earcup, around the acoustic loudspeaker plate.

This work constitutes a public prior-art disclosure made in France and in the United States. All technical elements are intentionally published in order to prevent any patent appropriation by third parties.

Abstract

This document presents an ultra-low-latency wireless audio headphone architecture intended for metal detectors, in particular pulse-induction (PI), VLF, or multifrequency systems requiring fast, stable, and dynamic audio restitution.

Unlike conventional wireless headphones using an external housing, a connecting cable, an add-on module, or electronics installed through major modification of the shell, the proposed system integrates the radio module, control electronics, user-interface elements, and loudspeaker directly on or around the internal acoustic plate located on the ear side.

This architecture avoids any functional re-drilling or major rework of the main external headphone shell, naturally protects the electronic components within the internal volume of the earcup, and preserves ergonomics compatible with field use. The system is associated with a specific ultra-low-latency digital transmission, with a representative latency on the order of 400 μ s and an audio refresh period typically close to 1.6 ms.

This publication constitutes a prior-art disclosure intended to prevent any equivalent patent filing by third parties on the principle of protected internal integration of a low-latency wireless audio module inside a headphone earcup, particularly when this integration uses the loudspeaker acoustic plate as a mechanical, acoustic, and electronic support.

Keywords: wireless headphones, low latency, metal detector, pulse induction, PI, ENIGMA, PI², PI³, PI⁴, integrated RF module, acoustic plate, protected earcup, real-time audio, prior art.

1 Introduction

Modern metal detectors, especially pulse-induction (PI) detectors, use audio as a real-time information interface. Sound is not only used to indicate the presence of a target; it also conveys fine variations in magnitude, tone, envelope, and dynamics related to the target, the ground, sweep speed, and processing algorithms.

In this context, conventional wireless audio transmission may be insufficient. General-purpose audio protocols, especially those designed for music or telephony, often introduce latency, buffering, or codec processing that is incompatible with immediate restitution of useful information.

This document describes a specific low-latency wireless headphone architecture in which the electronic module is integrated directly into the earcup, on or around the loudspeaker acoustic plate. The objective is twofold: to obtain fast audio restitution suitable for metal detectors, and to eliminate external housings or cables that could weaken the assembly during field use.

This publication is intentionally made as a prior-art disclosure in order to preserve freedom of use for this concept.

2 Limitations of Existing Solutions

Conventional wireless solutions generally have one or more of the following limitations:

- significant latency due to the protocol or audio codec;
- external receiver housing attached to the headphones or to the detector;
- audio cable connecting a receiver module to the headphones;
- controls and connectors placed on the external surface of the headphones;
- major mechanical modification of the shell;
- increased exposure to shocks, rubbing, branches, rain, sand, or mud.

These limitations are particularly detrimental for metal detectors. The user moves continuously, sweeps the ground, interprets micro-variations in sound, and must preserve an immediate relationship between coil position and audio response.

A suitable solution must therefore combine:

- extremely low latency;
- dynamic sound restitution;
- robust mechanics;
- compact integration;
- absence of an obstructive external module.

3 Proposed Architecture

3.1 General Principle

The proposed system consists of integrating the wireless audio module directly into the earcup of protective or listening headphones, using the internal area located around the loudspeaker.

The architecture may include:

- a perforated internal acoustic plate;
- a loudspeaker placed behind or at the center of this plate;
- a radio electronic board integrated into the internal volume of the earcup;
- user controls accessible from the ear side;
- one or more light indicators;
- a charging or maintenance connector;
- an internal battery or energy-storage element;
- an integrated RF antenna.

The internal acoustic plate thus becomes a multifunctional interface: it contributes to sound output, loudspeaker retention, electronic integration, and mechanical protection of the assembly.

3.2 Absence of External Module

Unlike an architecture in which a radio receiver is attached to the outside of the headphones or connected by cable, the proposed system requires no visible external housing. The main external shell may remain compact and does not require heavy functional rework.

This arrangement reduces the risks of:

- snagging;
- tearing-off;
- breakage;
- local infiltration associated with an external modification;
- ergonomic discomfort while wearing the headphones.

3.3 Protection by the Earcup

The earcup forms a naturally protected volume through the shell, the ear cushion, and the internal geometry of the headphones. The electronic components are therefore less exposed to direct impacts, rubbing, projections, and accidental handling.

This protection is particularly relevant for metal detectors used in forests, on beaches, in mineralized ground, in gold prospecting, or in wet and abrasive environments.

4 Low-Latency Audio Transmission

The proposed architecture is not limited to mechanical integration. It is associated with a specific ultra-low-latency digital transmission adapted to the constraints of metal detectors.

In a representative implementation, the effective latency is on the order of:

$$t_{\text{latency}} \approx 400 \mu\text{s}$$

The audio refresh period is typically on the order of:

$$T_{\text{refresh}} \approx 1.6 \text{ ms}$$

corresponding to an update frequency close to:

$$f_{\text{refresh}} \approx 625 \text{ Hz}$$

These values preserve an almost immediate temporal relationship between the coil passing over a target and the user's sound perception. The headphones therefore operate as a real-time extension of the detector, rather than as a simple general-purpose wireless audio peripheral.

In this approach, the transmitted information may be parametric rather than a complete audio stream. It may include, for example, a magnitude, a tone, a modulation, or a status information. This philosophy reduces the useful data rate, limits latency, and prioritizes freshness of transmitted information.

5 Main Advantages

The proposed architecture provides several combined advantages:

1. **Mechanical robustness.**

The electronics are placed in a protected area, with no external radio housing and no visible audio cable.

2. **Industrial simplicity.**

The main external headphone shell can be retained or only slightly modified, reducing tooling costs, re-drilling operations, and add-on parts.

3. **Field ergonomics.**

The absence of external protrusions reduces the risk of snagging on branches, clothing, bags, or prospecting equipment.

4. **Fast audio restitution.**

Latency on the order of 400 μ s and refresh close to 1.6 ms help preserve useful micro-variations in the detection signal.

5. **Acoustic integration.**

The perforated internal plate preserves sound output toward the ear while serving as a functional support for the loudspeaker and electronic elements.

6. **Compatibility with several detection technologies.**

The principle is applicable to PI, VLF, and multifrequency detectors when audio information must be restituted with high dynamics.

6 Figures

Figure 2: Exploded CAD view of the earcup showing the integration of the acoustic plate, loudspeaker, electronic board, and internal shell.

Figure 3: CAD view of the internal side of the earcup showing the perforated acoustic area, user controls, and integration without any apparent external module.

Figure 4: Assembled prototype of the low-latency wireless headphones showing the integration of controls and acoustic output on the ear side.

Figure 5: Rear view of the headphones showing the absence of an external radio housing and the preservation of a compact external shell.

Figure 6: Close-up view of the earcup and cushion showing the natural protection of the electronics by the internal headphone volume.

7 Applications

The main application concerns metal detectors requiring fast and informative sound restitution, including:

- pulse-induction detectors;
- VLF detectors;
- multifrequency detectors;
- gold prospecting systems;
- detectors used on beaches or in mineralized ground;
- detectors integrating dynamic ground tracking or advanced sound classification.

The concept may also be extended to other professional or industrial headphones requiring protected radio electronics, low latency, absence of external cable, and high mechanical robustness.

8 Scope of the Prior Art

This publication constitutes a technical prior-art disclosure. It explicitly describes:

1. wireless audio headphones intended for metal detectors;
2. integration of the electronic module inside the earcup;
3. placement on or around the internal acoustic plate;
4. absence of an external radio module;
5. absence of a visible audio cable;
6. limitation of functional modifications to the external shell;
7. natural protection of the electronics by the cushion and internal volume of the earcup;
8. specific low-latency digital transmission;
9. representative effective latency on the order of 400 μ s;
10. audio refresh typically close to 1.6 ms;
11. possible transmission of compact audio parameters such as magnitude, tone, or modulation;
12. use adapted to PI, VLF, and multifrequency detectors.

The subject matter of this publication is not limited to the exact geometry of the prototype shown. It more broadly covers any architecture in which low-latency RF audio electronics are integrated inside an earcup, using the internal acoustic plate as a mechanical, acoustic, and functional area, in order to avoid an external housing and major modification of the shell.

Any subsequent attempt to file a patent covering these principles, or an equivalent combination, would lack novelty or inventive step in view of this disclosure.

9 Conclusion

Low-latency wireless audio headphones for metal detectors have been presented. The proposed architecture integrates the radio module, control electronics, indicators, loudspeaker, and user-interface elements into the internal area of the earcup, on or around the loudspeaker acoustic plate.

This approach eliminates the external radio housing, avoids the visible audio cable, protects the electronics through the headphone structure itself, and preserves a compact external shell. Combined with latency on the order of 400 μ s and refresh close to 1.6 ms, it enables the headphones to operate as a real-time extension of the detector.

This publication is intentionally made as prior art in order to preserve freedom of use of this concept in the metal detector industry and in any application requiring robust, compact, ultra-low-latency wireless headphones.

Author Contributions

A. Tartar designed the overall architecture of the low-latency wireless headphones, the internal mechanical integration, the use of the acoustic plate as a functional support, the protected ear-side placement strategy, and the principle of fast digital audio transmission adapted to PI detectors.

Document Information

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